

THE ROLE OF PROBABILISTIC PREDICTION STRATEGY IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION

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ANNOTATION

In field simultaneous interpretation, prediction—whether as a tactic or a phenomenon—plays a key role and has attracted a lot of attention from academics. The study of anticipation is far from being systematic and comprehensive, and it can be challenging to get diverse experts to agree on some topics. This article addresses some fundamental questions about expectation in simultaneous interpretation in the hopes that it would help readers better comprehend prediction in simultaneous interpretation and encourage more research on the topic.

Keywords: *simultaneous interpretation, methods, communication, probabilistic forecasting mechanism, redundancy, target and source language.*

Introduction

The probabilistic forecasting strategy in simultaneous interpretation refers to the translator's attempt to anticipate and plan out lexical, grammatical, and phonetic elements of the speaker's speech before they are spoken, based on information that has already been received and processed (i.e., translated). Identifying any elements of speech in the speaker's text is one of the probabilistic forecasting techniques. This approach is particularly effective when the statement's major idea and semantic content are concentrated at the conclusion of the phrase.

Methods

According to G.V. Chernov, the probabilistic forecasting mechanism is a psycholinguistic mechanism that provides simultaneous interpretation¹. In the process of the incoming information, the interpreter can guess about the possible options for the end of the communicative situation, starting from the linguistic material that has already been heard before. Probabilistic forecasting, as a mechanism underlying the processing of information by a interpreter in a foreign language, is multilevel, hierarchically organized, in which units of each level are associated with conditional probabilities: at the levels of a syllable, word, syntagma, utterance, coherent message, and also at the level of a communicative situation . The higher the message redundancy, the higher the probability of correctly predicting its development at each of the selected levels. The opposite is also true: the less redundancy, the greater the density of information in a message, the lower the probability of correctly predicting its development. V.V. Sdobnikov and O.V. Petrova write that language redundancy manifests itself at different levels². For example, in the phonemic language: in Russian, a vowel must go through one or two consonants or redundancy at the grammatical level. Simultaneous interpreter perceives speech (recognition by key reference points) just due to the required level of redundancy, thus providing the possibility of probabilistic prediction. The redundancy of language, in turn, is divided into objective and subjective. An objectively redundant message (for example, a report at a chemical symposium) subjectively for a given interpreter may have a very low degree of redundancy, which violates the probabilistic forecasting mechanism, that is, becomes an obstacle to simultaneous translation. Thus, the real redundancy of the message for the simultaneous interpreter depends on his knowledge in this area and on the experience of translating special messages. The presence of context increases redundancy, which enables a simultaneous interpreter to carry out probabilistic

¹ Чернов, Г.В. Теория и практика синхронного перевода / Г.В. Чернов. – М.: Международные отношения, 1978. – 208 с.

² Сдобников, В.В., Петрова, О.В. Теория перевода: учебник для студентов лингвистических вузов и факультетов иностранных языков / В.В. Сдобников, О.В. Петрова. – М.: АСТ: Восток-Запад, 2007. – 448 с.

forecasting with greater accuracy.¹ He and other researchers established the causes of redundancy: 1) the repetition of certain elements in the flow of speech; 2) the interdependence of the linguistic components of the message. The fact that the sequence of message components (sounds, words, phrases, sentences and meanings) is formed on the basis of certain rules, which makes them interdependent, and boils down to the fact that the source of the message is repeated. Such conclusions are also the main provisions of the theory of communication (Chernov, 1980).

Conclusion.

Extralinguistic probabilistic forecasting is a topic we may discuss. The primary stressors impacting this cognitive function are the speaker's pronunciation, speech rate (and the lag caused by the interpreter as a result), and the absence of information redundancy, which prevents speech compression. We believe that translators must learn to predict the conclusion of an utterance based on the beginning of the speech in order to improve the stress resistance of the cognitive process of probabilistic forecasting. Additionally, simultaneous interpreters may be able to predict how a speech could go by drawing on their own prior knowledge.

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¹ Пиотровский, Р.Г. Информационные измерения языка / Р.Г. Пиотровский. – Л.: Наука, 1968. – 116 с